

ABBREVIATIONS IN MODERN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

¹Safarova M.Z.

2nd year student of UzFinPI,

²Sharipova M.K.

Scientific adviser.

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ABSTRACT

The paper indicates the role and place of abbreviations in the modern Russian language, it is emphasized that abbreviations serve as the basis of the law of speech economy. The conducted research shows the effectiveness of the use of abbreviations, as well as the negative and positive aspects of abbreviation formation in modern Russian. In addition, it talks about borrowed abbreviations, as well as their codification.

Abbreviation - (Italian *abbreviatura*, from Latin *abbrevio* - I shorten) - a noun consisting of truncated words included in the original phrase, or of truncated components of the original compound word. The abbreviation is literally "reduction". [5,9] Abbreviations in common use are words formed from syllables, the initial sounds of words, or the names of their initial letters. An example is the words UN - the United Nations, emergency - an emergency, the CIS - the Commonwealth of Independent States and others [4, 72].

The types of abbreviations are varied: alphabetic - a word from the first letters of phrases - UFO; alpha-sound - the word is obtained partly from the first letters, partly from the first sounds - traffic police; sound, acronym (also from the first letters, but pronounced like a normal word) - university

In addition, abbreviations include: compound words - formed from several words - maternity hospital, television network, spare part; graphic abbreviations - etc., i.e., because, so-called; the abbreviation is mixed - an abbreviation is added to the beginning of the word - KamAZ.

Why do abbreviations appear in the language? First of all, because the law of speech economy is one of the main laws of language development. The speaker and writer is always trying to save their efforts. Successful abbreviations not only shorten a complex name, save pronunciation time and space for writing, but also enrich the language with new words, more capaciously and briefly naming the subject. Abbreviation words can become so independent that their decoding is forgotten. For example, a registry office - a record of acts of civil status - is the name of the institution in which marriages are registered.

However, what the writer Tatyana Tolstaya called "the itch of naming and renaming" is now happening in the language. Too many one-day abbreviations are invented by politicians, journalists, they are used in print or on television.

As an example, I will cite those abbreviations that were used in the "creeping line" of the channel "Russia 24" only for 1 day - Ministry of Emergency Situations, IOC, OI, Southern Federal District, NAC, SK, Housing and Public Utilities, UK, Road Traffic Accidents, Traffic Police, Moscow Ring Road, ISS, UES, World Cup, European Championship, VTB.

I did a little research, asking to decipher the phrase that I read on this channel - "The Ministry of Emergency Situations warns: emergencies are possible in the Southern Federal District, the Far Eastern Federal District and the Central Federal District." Of the 30 surveyed students in grade 9, only seven people (23%) were able to correctly decipher all the words. Out of 10 teachers - 8 (80%).

As an example, we can cite such abbreviations as CD (compact disk), VIP (very important person), SMS (short message service), while when attached to a foreign language abbreviation of a Russian word, semantic redundancy is often observed: VIP-person; CD-ROM; SMS message.

Borrowed abbreviations at the initial stage of their existence in the language require a mandatory comment. An interesting example is the word "spa", or "SPA". Not quite understanding the meaning of the word, many nevertheless actively use it. There are several ways to explain its meaning. According to one, it originated from the name of the town of Spa in Belgium, famous for its thermal springs. According to another version, this is an abbreviation of the Latin phrases sanus per aquam, solus per aquas, sanitas per aquas, which means "health through water" or "health through water."

When abbreviating the names of enterprises and institutions, the compilers of official documents often neglect the requirements of euphony, often using "monster words". Here are just some examples from G. N. Sklyarevskaya's Dictionary of Abbreviations of the Modern Russian Language (M., 2004):

- GAVS - Humanitarian Academy of the Armed Forces;
- MIBF - Moscow International Book Fair;
- MOPS - International Organization of Consumers Unions;
- TsDUB - Central Spiritual Administration of Buddhists;
- RAGS - Russian Academy of Public Administration;
- CSOs are mandatory civic responsibility.

It is known that the first place in the famous Guinness Book of Records belongs to the Soviet abbreviation "NIIOMTPLABOPARMBETZHEL BETRABS BORMONIMONKONOTDTEHSTROMONTUPRASIASSR", which means - Research Laboratory of Concrete Reinforcement and Reinforced Concrete Works for the Construction of Prefabricated Monolithic and Monolithic Structures of the Technology Department of the Construction and Assembly Department of the Academy of Construction and Architecture of the USSR .

There are also many neoplasms in the documents of our school, for example:

- USE - unified state exam,*
- SEC - State Examination Commission,*
- RTsOI - regional information processing center,*
- KIM - control and measuring materials,*
- SanPiN - sanitary rules and regulations,*

GEF - Federal State Educational Standards

Abbreviations are often criticized. Some native speakers consider them insufficiently normative, inferior words. However, it must be borne in mind that the Russian language has adopted some of these words, they are necessary for it, sometimes it is impossible to do without them. One of the main reasons for their development is that abbreviations are an effective means of saving speech resources.

However, the recent increase in the number of abbreviations, in my opinion, indicates that the primitive language is, unfortunately, becoming a style of communication. This is helped by the desire of many media outlets for wide popularity in any way, and the low level of taste, style and sense of proportion among some people involved in the creation of official documents.

In conclusion, we repeat once again: abbreviations, when used appropriately and correctly, allow you to optimize verbal communication, reducing the efforts of the speaker or writer. Most of them are firmly included in the Russian language. At the same time, the immoderate and thoughtless use of abbreviations can lead to misunderstanding of the statement, reveal a lack of linguistic taste, and cause an undesirable reaction from the reader or listener.

Bibliography:

Lipatov A.T. On the word-formation possibilities of abbreviations // Russian Language at School, No. 5. -M., 1987. - S.83-87.

Ozhegov S.I. Lexicology. Lexicography. A culture of speech. - M., 1974. -S. 20-36.

Dictionary of business terms. Internet - resource "Akademik.ru", 2001. But linguists know that for a wide audience it is recommended to use only generally accepted abbreviations. The use of abbreviations accepted only in a narrow professional circle requires mandatory decoding. In the case of using a non-standard abbreviation, at the beginning of the text, a decoding of the abbreviation should be given, for example: National Anti-Terrorism Committee (NAC), etc.

Many abbreviations are borrowed into Russian from other languages. Most often, at first they retain the Latin spelling, and then many words are adapted to the Russian language.

References:

1. Липатов А.Т. О словообразовательных возможностях аббревиатур // Русский язык в школе, №5. –М., 1987. - С.83-87.
2. Ожегов С.И. Лексикология. Лексикография. Культура речи. — М., 1974. -С. 20-36.
3. Словарь бизнес - терминов. Интернет - ресурс «Академик.ру», 2001.
4. Шарипова М.К. Аббревиатуры периода Независимости и их роль в обогащении русского и узбекского языков. // СамДУ илмий тадқиқотлар ахборотномаси, №4. – Самарканд, 2011. – С.71-73.
5. Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь. Под ред. В.Н.Ярцевой. - М.: Советская энциклопедия, 1990. – С.9.
6. Складневская Г.Н. Словарь сокращений современного русского языка. -М.: ЭКСМО, 2004. - 405 с.

7. Словарь иностранных слов/ Под.ред. Ф.Н.Петрова. 13-е изд. - М.: Русский язык, 1986. - 608 с.
8. Куц Н.Г. Аббревиатуры в современном русском языке – за и против. // <https://nsportal.ru/shkola/russkiy-yazyk/library/2013/08/12/abbreviatury-v-sovremennom-russkom-yazyke-za-i-protiv>